

ANALYSIS OF STUDIES ON THE JUSTIFICATION OF THE PARAMETERS OF THE BRAKE SYSTEM OF AUTO-TRACTOR TRAILERS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the analysis of studies on the justification of the parameters of the brake system of auto-tractor trailers. According to him, the scientific work carried out by several scientists around the world was studied. As a result of the study, various factors affecting the system were studied when justifying the parameters of the braking system of road trains

Key words: Truck, tractor trailer, tractor, trailer, brake, pneumatics, pipes, speed, drive

INTRODUCTION

The use of vehicles is one of the pillars of the global economy and one of the most important means of transportation for mankind [1], [2]. However, one of the important factors in the quality of human life and the quality of goods transported when using vehicles is the braking system.

In order to avoid a significant reduction in the carrying capacity of cotton, silage, hay, etc., which are much smaller than the bulk, and to fully exploit the capabilities of the tractor, the vehicle must have a large trailer. Such vehicles may include only heavy duty trucks, trailers, increased payload, oversized road trains with an increased body size.

In order to fulfill these tasks in accordance with the state program for the implementation of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of human dignity and active good neighborliness" based on the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, Goal 22: Continuation of the industrial policy aimed at ensuring the sustainability of the national economy and increasing the share of industry in GDP, organizing the production of agricultural machinery in

Chirchik into a single industrial cluster in accordance with paragraph 79 of the Increase in industrial production by 1.4 times Priorities section, goals and objectives have been set. Part 2 describes the mechanisms for organizing the production of agricultural machinery and trailers.

Based on these tasks, a lot of research has been carried out to substantiate the parameters of the braking system of road trains and study the principles of their operation. Based on the data obtained, a large amount of literature was analyzed to justify the braking parameters of a number of road trains.

When designing a vehicle's braking system, braking performance must first be considered. The braking system should stop or reduce the speed of the car as quickly as possible, and the direction of the car in any road conditions should be stable and controllable [3]. A key aspect of good braking is braking balance. This happens when each wheel brakes in proportion to the weight it carries [4]. If this is achieved, the vehicle can effectively use the friction of the road, and the wheels will have a minimum braking distance without slip. Wheel lock leads to loss of directional stability, especially when it occurs on drive axles or trailer axles, since a locked wheel cannot provide stabilizing lateral forces [5].

Most performance studies and visual inspections of an air brake system indirectly relate brake chamber pressure to output torque, brake pad temperature, pushrod travel, etc. [6], [7]. Pneumatic brake systems are commonly used in vehicles such as buses, trucks and tractor-trailers [8]. Over 85% of vehicles in the US are equipped with S-cam drum brakes [9]. Proper operation of the vehicle's braking system is crucial not only for the safety of the vehicle itself, but also for other vehicles and passengers in motion. An accident involving a vehicle can lead not only to economic losses of transported goods, but also to death of people.

The main elements of the pneumatic brake system are the compressor and reservoirs, the brake valve, quick-acting and accelerating valves, main pipelines, brake chambers and clearance adjusters. Elements of the air brake system, their specifications, principles of operation, maintenance and test details can be found in [10], [11] and [12].

Srivatsan Ramarathnam, Sandeep Dhar, Swaroop Darbha and K. R. Rajagopal propose a simple scheme for leak detection and leak estimation in terms of infiltrated air mass flow based on brake pressure output measurements at full brake pressure and supply pressure [13].

In [14], the line of the pneumatic brake system was studied, which is an important factor affecting the pressure response time in the pneumatic brake system. Based on a research experiment with pneumatic brake pipelines, the influence of the length, diameter of the pipeline, initial pressure and supply pressure on the response time in

the pipeline was analyzed using the correlation analysis method. It has been found that the length of the pipeline is the most important factor influencing the reaction time of a pressure change. Based on the method of multi-parameter analysis, the influence of experimental parameters on the time of pressure change in the pipeline was analyzed. On the basis of experimental data, a calculation formula was derived using the method of dimensional analysis, which allows you to select the parameters of pipelines and the entire pneumatic brake system.

One of the effective ways to speed up the response time of a brake drive is to install an accelerating valve in the control lines of a two-wire brake drive [15]. With the help of a mathematical model developed earlier in [16], the influence of the distance from the installation site of the AC to the brake valve on the speed of the drive was studied.

Thus, foreign and domestic scientists G. Yimin, M. Ehsani, E. Esmailzadeh, A. Goodarzi and M. Behmadi, P. Hart, S. Shaffer and G. Alexander, R. B. GmbH, S. Williams and R. Knippling, Bendix, Srivatsan Ramarathnam, Sandeep Dhar, Swaroop Darbha and K. R. Rajagopal, Zhiqiang Gu, Shiyu Hu, Fan Yang, Rui Yang, and Jian Hua, A.A. Shermukhamedov, V.A. Topalidi, K.K. Khodjiev and others.

They defined various methods of research, calculation and justification of the parameters of vehicle brakes. However, in these studies, the complexity of the external impact (road conditions), the definition of parameters by type of load, the parameters of its safe and high-quality operation have not been sufficiently studied

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